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Marine spatial planning for siting wave-powered aquaculture farms

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Abstract

Recent advancements in sustainable off-shore technologies such as wave-powered aquaculture farms (WPAFs) require increased attention to their placement and interactions with neighboring industries. Using marine spatial planning (MSP) techniques, this project aims to identify promising locations for a WPAF setup, with enough wave power generation potential, a suitable environment for the target aquaculture species, and minimal potential conflicts with other industries. To do so, GIS (geographic information system) software is leveraged to analyze and visualize data on oceanic conditions, bathymetry, energy infrastructure, and areas of high fishing traffic. Oceanic conditions including temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, and current speed are used to determine the carrying capacity (the ability of a region to support a fish species) of a certain location, while wave energy period and significant wave height are used to predict the power generation. In addition, this work utilizes publicly accessible sources of GIS data and open-source software to make these techniques available to a wide array of stakeholders who might benefit from incorporating MSP into their work. The application of MSP to wave-powered aquaculture allows different geographic locations to be analyzed, and an overall cost model developed to rank potential sites and determine promising locations for this type of project. The MSP analysis is done for the Northeast coast of the United States including the federal and state waters of Delaware through Maine. The results of this analysis identify several sites along the northern coast of Maine as ideal locations for a wave-powered Atlantic salmon aquaculture farm, and two trends stand out as important considerations for future research and planning. Results of our analyses indicate that the cost of a farm, which includes all location-dependent costs such as the wave energy converters (WECs) and transportation, is heavily determined by the availability of wave energy, and therefore decreases further from shore despite the slight increase in transportation costs. They also show that many of the areas in the southern region of study do not meet the carrying capacity requirement for the aquaculture farm or conflict with one of the many existing industries in the regions around New York and Massachusetts. This significantly limits the potential sites and leads to relatively few potential farm sites, which are located further north along the coast.

Keywords: fisheries; marine spatial planning; offshore aquaculture; qgis; wave energy converters

1. Introduction

The development of new marine technologies, such as wave energy and offshore aquaculture, holds real potential in addressing our reliance on fossil fuels and unsustainable food production systems. But the real-world implementation of these projects is complex, and careful planning and coordination with stakeholders will be critical

to maximize a project's potential and avoid conflicts with neighboring industries such as fisheries and offshore wind developments. Coordination like this already had success in projects like the Block Island Wind Farm, where input from local fisheries influenced the siting of turbines [1, 2], and will become even more important as various industries expand off our shores.

This work aims to develop a GIS (geographic information system) mapping tool using marine spatial planning (MSP) techniques, with a specific focus on co-locating wave energy converters (WECs) and offshore aquaculture farms. MSP is a process used to make informed decisions about the use of marine resources. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. First, a review of the methodology for this study is presented. It includes defining the study scope, selecting data sources and software to be used, processing and analyzing the data in question, and using geospatial data with Python to create a more complex cost model. Following methodology, the results of the case study and overall conclusions are discussed. Fig. 1 provides an overview of the analysis process, and maps referenced throughout the paper are included in the appendix.

2. Methodology

Fig. 1. Flowchart of steps in mapping and analysis process.

2.1. *Selecting scope, data, and software*

This paper focuses on the Atlantic coast of the northeastern United States, which includes the states of Maine, New Hampshire, Massachusetts, Rhode Island, Connecticut and New York, as defined by the Northeast Sea Grant [3]. The region within the scope of the study includes state waters, within 5.6 km (3 nautical miles) of shore, and federal waters, within 370 km (200 NM) of shore, of these and adjacent states. This region is roughly bounded by 38.45°N 75.78°W and 45.19°N 65.70°W, as shown in Fig. 2.

Although some of the analysis within GIS software can be done on a continuous basis, the cost model developed in Python requires individual points across the region. The cost model samples each of these points and calculates a dollar value for location-dependent costs such as transportation and WEC deployment based on the distance from shore and wave climate of that location. For this “brute-force” approach, a resolution of 0.1° longitude and latitude was selected to balance the precision of the results with the need for reasonable computational time.

Geospatial data needed for mapping and analysis is obtained from several publicly available sources. Raster datasets, which provide continuous data on a quantity of interest across a region, including current speed, salinity, and wave height are used to identify areas that meet the biological requirements of fish and sufficient power output from WECs. Vector datasets, which describe points, lines, and regions, such as offshore wind lease areas, shipping lanes, and state and federal waters, are used to find suitable sites and avoid conflicts with other offshore industries.

QGIS, an open-source GIS software, is used for much of the processing, analysis, and mapping layouts. Although not currently the industry standard, QGIS has all the features necessary for this project and is more accessible to a wide range of users than alternative software options.

2.2. *Processing and analyzing data*

Several steps are first completed to pre-process and standardize data sets before further analysis. These include file conversion from proprietary GIS formats, clipping the data to include only the project scope, re-projecting to a standard CRS (coordinate reference system), in this case WGS 84 (EPSG:4326), and interpolation of conditions that may be distributed as individual data points into continuous vector datasets.

Within QGIS, several operations exist for initial analysis of oceanic conditions and identifying areas of potential conflict. Generating contour lines of oceanic condition raster datasets and filtering by which areas meet certain biological requirements both help to visualize the distribution of conditions across a region and identify sites that meet the selected criteria. Fig. 3 shows several oceanic conditions of interest along with contour lines. Raster datasets of

other ocean activities can be used to highlight areas where existing industries or high vessel traffic could lead to more conflicts. Fig. 4 shows the distribution of several of these industries, and it is easy to see areas, such as the coast of Cape Cod, where several already occupy the same space.

The cost model is then used to evaluate different valid points and determine the location-dependent costs for the farm including WECs and travel [4]. The model considers several sizes of farms, each with a constant stocking density and fish yield. This more complex model is easier to complete in Python, so GIS datasets are integrated into the Python model using the GeoPandas package. This method allows a Python model to query data from different locations, run an analysis, and return results in a GIS format that can then be mapped in QGIS. Using GeoPandas gives the added flexibility of a complete programming environment and packages to facilitate optimization and other analysis tools, while still leveraging geospatial datasets and mapping capabilities.

3. Results

Optimal sites are identified based on suitable environmental conditions, minimal conflicts with other industries, and a lower cost for location-dependent expenses. Several sites are identified along the coast of Maine, near Acadia National Park, that avoid many of the crowded areas further south and benefit from more wave activity further offshore. Fig. 5 shows these locations and their different modeled costs. The labels near each point indicate the cost as a multiple of the optimal location. For a small farm of five net pens and a fish yield of about 900 tonnes, the optimal location, which is about 40 km southeast of Bar Harbor, ME, would have a wave energy potential of 11 kW/m, and would cost \$43M. In comparison, a site in the same region but only 13 km from Bar Harbor would have a wave energy potential of 8.6 kW/m and cost \$110M [5].

The various conflicts considered in this study significantly limit the number of locations suitable for the development of an aquaculture farm. New offshore wind farms and commercial fisheries, an often-vocal group, crowd many of the regions that would otherwise be good for offshore aquaculture such as the coast of Cape Cod. Shipping and recreational boats are also common further south near New York City and along Long Island. As a result, valid results generally occur further north along the coast of Maine where there is less existing infrastructure, and the environment is suitable for salmon farming.

The cost of an aquaculture farm is strongly influenced by the cost of the WECs, and therefore locations further from shore become significantly cheaper due to the higher significant wave heights creating sufficient power with fewer WECs. Areas near shore and in sheltered waters suffer significantly from decreased wave activity, and the cost savings of going further offshore far outweigh the additional transportation costs to get there. The gains from going further offshore, however, are limited by the maximum depth at which net pens can be installed (generally 70 meters deep). In areas where the continental shelf extends far offshore this may not be an issue, but most of the identified optimal sites along the coast of Maine are limited by this constraint.

4. Conclusion

MSP is becoming an increasingly important field as our reliance on marine resources for as food and energy grows, and more industries expand offshore. This work provided one example of what an MSP process could look like to identify potential regions for aquaculture in the Northeast while reducing the industry's reliance on fossil fuels by co-locating WECs and avoiding conflicts with neighboring industries. By using public geospatial data, QGIS, and Python, several potential sites along the coast of Maine were identified as promising locations for wave-powered aquaculture. In addition, several trends were identified including a significant reduction in cost associated with the larger waves that occur further offshore, and a lack of potential sites in more southern regions due to insufficient environmental conditions and crowding from other industries. Future work on this project aims to make these results more accessible to a large set of stakeholders through building an interactive website, and to expand the scope to include integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA).

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Appendix

Fig. 2. Scope of project and grid of sampled points along the northeast coast.

Fig. 3. Conditions considered in carrying capacity and cost models.

Fig. 4. Potential conflicts with other offshore industries including proposed offshore wind areas.

Fig. 5. Comparison of cost model results for points that meet all requirements and avoid conflicts.

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